

GUIDELINES TO IMPLEMENT SEPARATION MINIMA AND METHODS

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BUBBLES

DEFINING THE BUILDING BASIC BLOCKS FOR A U-SPACE SEPARATION MANAGEMENT SERVICE

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Abstract

This document describes a methodology to automatically compute separation minima and methods for the Unmanned Aerial Systems (UAS) application use cases representative for the BUBBLES project. The methodology exploits the algorithms for collision risk analysis presented in BUBBLES Deliverable D4.1 [1] and extends the current state of the art by proposing methods based on representative trajectories representing the UAS Concept of Operations (ConOps) developed by the project in Deliverable D3.1 [2] and by integrating Artificial Intelligence models and techniques to generate such trajectories and to estimate trajectory-based separation minima and methods.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Objectives

The goal of this deliverable is to describe the development of models and a methodology for separation management in a set of relevant UAS operations. More specifically, the proposed methodology aims at integrating trajectory-based collision risk analysis and Artificial Intelligence (AI) models and techniques to support the BUBBLES U-space Separation Management Service ConOps.

1.2 Scope

This deliverable is focused on a methodology for automatic computation of separation minima and methods for UAS in a given use case and according to a predefined Target Level of Safety (TLS). This methodology integrates methods and algorithms for collision risk analysis described in BUBBLES Deliverable D4.1 [1] with AI techniques for trajectory generation and computation of separation minima and methods.

The deliverable provides some implementation details and fully describes an application of the proposed methodology to a specific use case. The methodology described in this document will be validated in WP5 and will contribute to define safety and performance requirements in WP6.

1.3 Defining the reference use case

In this document, a use case representing a typical scenario is used to illustrate the methodology and the expected results of the proposed method. The considered use case consists of a border control task in which several UAS are engaged in a set of missions. Mission parameters, such as volume of operation, number of UAS, trajectory types, etc. are provided so that a set of representative trajectories of the UAS executing such missions can be generated. Moreover, strategic mitigations, such as separation minima and methods, can be applied to the different trajectory types.

The main idea of the approach presented in this deliverable is that the generation of simulated trajectories and the collision risk model already presented in Deliverable D4.1 [1] can be used to build a database relating mission parameters with corresponding estimated collision rates.

This database will be used to train machine learning models and the corresponding trained models can be used in a black-box fashion (typical of most of these approaches) to predict new values for collision risk in the considered use case. The final output of the overall process will thus be a component able to return suitable settings for separation minima and methods given a specific TLS. More specifically, in the border control example, given the mission parameters and a TLS, the proposed method will return a suitable configuration of separation minima and methods associated to each phase of the mission for each UAS.

1.4 Structure of this document

This document is structured as follows:

- Section 1 introduces the objectives and scope of the document.
- Section 2 introduces the separation minima and methods applicable to UAS.
- Section 3 provides a formal definition of the specification of the use cases, including a numerical example.
- Section 4 formally defines the problems to be addressed.
- Section 5 describes the methodology to solve the specified problems, i.e. to assign separation minima and methods.
- Section 6 presents some implementation details and the results of applying the proposed methodology to the use case presented in Section 3.

1.5 Acronyms

ACAS	Airborne Collision Avoidance System
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ANN	Artificial Neural Networks
ATC	Air Traffic Control
ATM	Air Traffic Management
CA	Collision Avoidance
CFR	Collision-Free Region
ConOps	Concept of Operations
CPA	Closest Point of Approach
CVSM	Conventional Vertical Separation Minimum
DAA	Detect and Avoid
DMOD	Distance Modification
DNN	Deep Neural Networks
GAN	Generative Adversarial Neural Networks
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite Systems
ICAO	International Civil Aviation Organization
ML	Machine Learning
NDB	Non-Directional Beacon
RGCSPP	Review of General Concept of Separation Panel
RL	Reinforcement Learning
RTCA	Radio Technical Commission for Aeronautics
RWC	Remain Well Clear
SAA	Sense and Avoidance
SARP	Science And Research Panel
SST	Self-Separation Threshold

SVM	Support Vector Machines
TLS	Target Level of Safety
TSE	Total System Error
UAS	Unmanned Aerial System
UTM	U-Space Traffic Management
VOR	Very High Frequency Omnidirectional Range
WC	Well-Clear
	Work Package

2 Separation minima and methods

This section introduces some background in separation minima and methods mainly studied in the context of manned aircraft. Although the use of UAS in the BUBBLES project makes the problems and the solutions significantly different from manned aviation, the general concepts are described to highlight their role within U-space separation management services.

2.1 Separation minima

This deliverable proposes a new methodology exploiting AI techniques to set the separation method and minima for pairs of UAS flying in some scenarios defined by some ConOps. The first step to accomplish this goal is to define separation methods and minima that AI algorithms should decide upon. A risk-based methodology to determine separation minima was already introduced in Deliverable 4.1 [1]. An improved proposal of separation methods for UAS is now introduced.

Separation is the concept of preserving an aircraft outside a minimum distance from other aircraft in its surrounding area to reduce the risk of collision. This separation is usually maintained by some Air Traffic Control services (ATC) who apply some regulation defining the minimum separation to avoid conflicts between pairs of aircraft. Maintaining separation minima is crucial to ensure safety of UAS operations. Achieving some defined TLS for collisions between UAS and between UAS and manned is a key issue for the risk assessment of UAS operations and to integrate UAS in some airspaces.

Currently, there are no well-established and standardized UAS separation minima yet. UAS separation minima can be considered at two different time horizons: Remain Well Clear (RWC) separation considers a time horizon with time enough for ATC intervention, while Collision Avoidance (CA) separation consider a tighter time horizon in which an immediate avoidance manoeuvre is needed to avoid a collision.

RWC separation can be accomplished using tactical procedures coming from a separation service (ATC or U-space service) to keep a set of close aircrafts to a minimum distance and achieving an orderly flow of traffic. This separation requires a timeframe which is sufficient for the separation service to act. It can be calculated using the timeline of actions defined in D 4.1 [1], section 4. The timeline includes the tracking system latency, the U-space service response time, communication times between the separation service and the pilot, the pilot response time and the avoidance manoeuvre execution time. Since the protection volume for RWC resulting from these assumptions is high, several aircrafts can be involved in this volume.

CA separation consists of a set of emergency avoidance manoeuvres that must be performed in a short period of time as a last resort to avoid a mid-air collision. They are planned by the on-board equipment, usually referred as Detect and Avoid (DAA), without the intervention of any separation service. It can be considered a self-separation method. International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) has set the priority of these CA actions calculated by the on-board equipment (in a collaborative way with the DAA systems of other aircrafts) over any ATC order or clearance.

The RWC limit has been well defined for large-unmanned aircraft systems by ICAO. However, this definition is not appropriate for small-unmanned aircraft systems operating at low altitudes where the difference between RWC and CA limits is less clear. Some studies clearly deal with setting a RWC

separation minima for UAS [3], [4] and [5]. Some other studies [6] consider a tighter Self-Separation Threshold (SST). This is a variable boundary that depends on time, distance and a combination of time and distance. The SST is “the boundary around the UAS at which the self-separation function declares that action is needed to preclude a threat aircraft from penetrating the CA threshold, thereby maintaining self-separation and keeping the aircraft ‘well clear’ (sic) of each other”. Weinert [7] in his outline research toward a definition of a RWC for small-unmanned aircraft systems developed an airborne collision risk for midterm concepts of operations at low altitudes in non-terminal airspace.

BUBBLES project aims at determining the RWC distance by performing a risk analysis of the operation, obtaining a TLS. The goal of the TLS is to set an upper bound on the aspired level of risk. The proposal of TLS will be based on the SORA proposal for the number of fatal injuries to third parties on ground per flight hour. The collision risk model used in this work decomposes the collision risk as the product of two probabilities: frequency of conflicts and probability of conflict [8]. The conclusion of the BUBBLES study about the separation methods to be used in UAS is that these methods strongly rely on the types of operations performed by the aircraft and it is determined in a pairwise fashion: the key parameter is the type of trajectory performed by the pair of aircraft in conflict. The manoeuvrability capacity offered by UAS is much more diverse than a conventional manned aircraft, giving rise to a wide range of avoidance trajectories.

According to the previous presented approach, a unique separation minimum for any type of trajectory is not suitable for UAS, since there may be situations or flight phases in which the UAS remains stationary around some area for a long time (strong locality) and others in which it advances quickly towards another area (translations). This work proposes to establish the separation according to the trajectory that the UAS is following in each flight phase, discriminating between the trajectories already introduced in D4.1 [1].

2.2 Types of trajectories

Translational trajectories: They are similar to the ones used in manned aircraft as a polyline defined by a number of waypoints. They are commonly used in the en-route phase and they are also used by UAS to fly from the landing area to/from the operations’ volume. This type of path is not strictly limited to completely straight legs, but large arcs used for translational movements between distant waypoints.

Hovering / loitering: This trajectory consists of movements around a defined geographic zone, either due to a surveillance interest in that location or a stationary position between changes of operations. This trajectory is mainly used in UAS configured with a multi-copter frame, since they have the ability to make abrupt course changes at low translational velocities. This type of movement can also be performed by fixed-wing UAS executing circles with a fixed radius around a position. In this case, the trajectory is referred to as a loiter and the radius and the radius generated will be wider than the one defined for hovering.

Specific patterns: These trajectories include operations performed automatically and with a repetitive structure over a pre-defined area, e.g., some of the most commonly used are scan patterns for crop monitoring, and spiral patterns for search and rescue operations. The characteristic is that the trajectory should be defined by a plan flight.

Figure 2-1 Different type of UAS trajectories in a single mission.

2.3 Separation methods

2.3.1 Separation methods for translational trajectories

The criteria used for the definition of translational trajectories in UAS is the same traditionally used by manned aviation, therefore, the separation methods for these cases must be supported by all the experience gathered in manned aviation defined in the document ICAO PANS-ATM [9].

Vertical separation. It is accomplished by the ATC service by requiring the aircraft to fly at different levels, expressed in flight levels or altitudes. It strongly relies on altimeter setting procedures. In manned aviation the Conventional Vertical Separation Minimum (CVSM) should be a nominal 300 m (1 000 ft.) below FL 290 and a nominal 600 m (2 000 ft.) at or above this level. UAS has been defined in D 4.1 [1] for the different considered cases. In this deliverable, the vertical distance is limited by the error in the determination of the position that for each UAS is 51 m.

Lateral separation. It is the horizontal distance that ensures that aircrafts in converging trajectories are far apart from each other. It is established in different ways according to the method that aircraft positions are determined: (1) through position reports that positively indicate that aircraft are over different geographic locations. (2) Requiring aircraft to fly on specified tracks which are separated by a minimum amount appropriate to the navigation aid employed (VOR, NDB, GNSS/GNSS, VOR/GNSS).

Longitudinal separation. It is a minimum separation between two aircrafts flying in same or reciprocal trajectories (mostly in airways). This separation can be specified as a time or a distance. Longitudinal separation is usually achieved by speed changes of the conflicting aircraft. Given the great diversity of speeds that we may have in UAS it seems logical to determine this separation as a time to perform the required separation actions, and then converting it into a distance by multiplying it by the closure rate.

Figure 2-2 Representation of separation methods for translational trajectories.

2.3.2 Separation methods for UAS patterns

One of the reasons for the rise in the use of UAS is their ability to carry out specific flight missions with great precision and repeatability. These features, along with the manoeuvrability of the UAS, results in a large number of trajectories whose protection volume cannot be defined with a translational trajectory. To determine the separation method in those types of trajectories, we will make use of the attitude of the UAS. As defined in D4.1. [1], the average speed over a period of time Δt , to create a protection volume around that value.

Separations methods for hovering/loitering.

This type of trajectory consists in movements around a defined geographic zone within the limits defined by the characteristics of the UAS and operation, i.e., it is not possible to predict the exact positions of the UAS in its trajectory, but a limit on this volume exists and might be geofenced. The proposed separation is a circular envelope that must enclose any possible position of the UAS in a big period of time with a confidence interval of 2σ . The probabilistic radius can be replaced by a fixed value when the trajectory is geofenced. The separation will be obtained by multiplying the radius of this envelope by a safety factor. This envelope may move in time if the trajectory of the UAS is not completely stationary over the same area. The motion of the envelope will be calculated by applying an average velocity analysis on this type of trajectory. This average vector speed is close to zero when the UAS is always hovering over a small area.

Separations methods for specific patterns.

The objective of this type of trajectories is to perform repetitive operations on an area of interest. These trajectories can range from a scan trajectory for surveying work to spiral trajectories for search and rescue operations (see Figure 2-1). A previous study of the flight area, airspace characteristics and airspace segregation are necessary. However, this type of trajectories includes search and rescue operations that must be performed as soon as possible, so it is not possible to perform such an exhaustive planning, as well as the risk of collision with other aircraft performing similar operations increases.

Similarly, to the hovering trajectories, an envelope kind of separation is proposed. The main difference with hovering is that the average vector speed is higher, so the envelope will have a displacement in the direction of the resulting average speed. For example, the average speed of scans and the envelope motion is shown in the Figure 2-3.

Figure 2-3 Separation methods for UAS most common trajectories.

2.3.3 Pairwise separations

The analysis of these separation methods will be performed in a pairwise fashion by an automatic real-time U-space separation service, so we must consider the different types of conflicts that may occur:

Translational trajectory - translational trajectory: In this case, two aircraft coincide with a translational movement, so the method of separation to be carried out will depend on the angle of encounter and the speed between them. To intervene as minimally as possible in their missions, the U-space service will attempt a vertical separation as a first measure. If it is not possible, some lateral or longitudinal separation will be chosen.

Translational trajectory - UAS pattern trajectory: This case defines a situation in which one UAS is performing an automatic mission with a predefined trajectory pattern and the other aircraft is performing a translation. The envelope separation, determined by the trajectory pattern, applies as a separation method in this case.

UAS pattern trajectory - UAS pattern trajectory: In cases where both UAS are performing a trajectory defined by some well-defined pattern, the separation method will be based on the trajectory envelope, and the separation will be the sum of the radius of both envelopes.

2.3.4 Remarks on avoidance manoeuvres

Regarding avoidance manoeuvres to achieve the desired separation, we can consider two issues: which aircraft will perform the manoeuvre and which type of manoeuvres will be used.

With respect to the aircraft that will perform the manoeuvre, we propose the aircraft flying the translational movement will have the priority over aircraft performing stationary flights or patterns. As an exception, we also propose that manned aircraft or UAS on emergency missions will have priority over other aircrafts, so it corresponds to the other conflicting aircraft to yield or to perform the avoidance manoeuvre.

The type of avoidance manoeuvre for lateral separation depends on the type of aircraft.

Fixed wing aircrafts usually perform reciprocal turns with each aircraft altering its trajectory to one side in order to avoid the other aircraft as described in section 4.2 of D 4.1 [1]. Rotorcraft can also perform hovering or holding patterns to avoid aircraft performing translational movements.

3 Definition of use cases

In this document, we will use the term *use case* to denote a combination of different use cases (described in terms of ConOps as defined for example in Deliverable D3.1 [2]) and additional mission parameters, such as trajectory types.

The computational method described in this deliverable is based on a formal definition of use cases that is described in this section. This formal definition allows for implementing suitable data structures for the algorithms to compute separation minima and methods.

3.1 Formal definition of a use case

A formal definition of a use case is given by $\mathcal{S} = \langle \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{M}, f, \mathcal{C} \rangle$ is a tuple containing:

- a set of agents \mathcal{A} (each agent represents a particular UAS);
- a set of tasks (or missions) \mathcal{M} ;
- an agent-task assignment function f ;
- a set of global (i.e., use case-based) parameters \mathcal{C}

More specifically:

$\mathcal{A} = \{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n\}$ is the set of UAS agents and each agent α_i has an internal representation of its states S_i , a set of available actions that it can perform A_i , a transition function $\delta_i : S_i \times A_i \rightarrow S_i$ (or a probability distribution $P(s'|s, a)$) and an initial state $s_i^0 \in S_i$.

$\mathcal{M} = \{M_1, \dots, M_m\}$ is the set of tasks (or missions). Each mission $M_k = \langle name_k, params_k \rangle$ has a unique name identifier and a set of parameters expressed as $params_{k,j} = \langle attribute_{k,j}, value_{k,j} \rangle$ pairs.

$f : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathcal{M}$ is a function assigning one task (or mission) to each agent.

\mathcal{C} is a set of global environmental parameters in the form of $\langle attribute_l, value_l \rangle$ pairs.

The dynamic execution of a use case will consist in the movement of UAS in the environment to perform their missions. A global clock measuring time during the evolution of the use case from 0 to T is assumed.

All the UAS start their missions at time 0 and finish at time T . During the evolution of the use case, the UAS produce a set of trajectories (i.e., an evolution of their states over time).

To formalize such a set of trajectories, agent α_i executes the task $M_k = f(\alpha_i)$ starting at time 0 and ending at time T . During the mission period, agent α_i traverses the states s_i^0, \dots, s_i^T , and thus, it produces a trajectory in the environment $\tau_i = \langle s_i^0, \dots, s_i^T \rangle$ according to the mission goal $goal_k$. Each trajectory must be compliant with: i) the agent transition function, ii) the parameters of the mission to which the agent is assigned $params_{k,j}$, and iii) the global parameters of the use case \mathcal{C} . The generated trajectories will be used to estimate the collision risk. In most cases, such an analysis will be

performed by considering only a subset of the state variables S_i , namely the ones related to UAS position (possibly augmented with heading and velocity data).

3.2 Use case parameters

Some examples of parameters that have been identified to characterize a use case are illustrated in this section. Notice that in this context only the parameters that affect the trajectories generated by the UAS when executing their missions are relevant. Parameters not affecting the trajectories are not considered in this model, although they may be considered in some following phase of the risk assessment process.

The use case parameters are divided in three groups, relative to: 1) UAS, 2) Missions, 3) Operational environment.

UAS-related parameters

- characteristics of each type of drone
 1. multicopter: weight, Maximum Take Off Mass (MTOM in kg), dimensions, speed (max; min; average), acceleration
 2. fixed wing;
- maximum ground speed, acceleration
- manoeuvrability
- autonomy (maximum operation time)

Mission-related parameters

- Take off point: longitude and latitude in degrees
- Landing point: longitude and latitude in degrees
- List of waypoints: longitude and latitude in degrees (will define a list of mission segments)
- Trajectory type for each segment (see next sub-section for details)
- Duration of mission segments (hovering, pattern)
- Category: open, specific or certified

Environment-related parameters

- volume of operations (specific geographical area, minimum and maximum height))
- semantic map of the use case (relevant POI in the use case)
- set of mission specifications
- total number of UAS
- number of UAS for each type

The mission parameters can be specified either with specific values or with value ranges. In the latter case, suitable sampling procedures will be used to determine specific values when needed. Notice also that other parameters can be considered as well, according to the specification of the use case.

3.2.1 Trajectory types

An important aspect of the definition of the mission is the trajectory type. In the approach described in this document, mission operations are formed by a sequence of sub-trajectories, each one assuming

a specific trajectory type. The possible trajectory types for small UAS have been studied for example in and can be summarized as follows (see also Figure 3-1).

- Horizontal transit: rectilinear movement between two points
- Hover: movements around a point of interest
- Patterns
 1. Creeping line – scan
 2. Sector
 3. Spiral
 4. Random
 5. (more)

Figure 3-1 Trajectory types

The methodology described in the next section will take the trajectory types into account when generating representative trajectories for the given mission. In general, each generated trajectory will be a composition of several sub-trajectory generated according to the specified trajectory type.

In this way, the collision risk model takes into account the mission parameters and in particular the trajectory types defining each mission.

3.3 Example of use case definition

This section provides a specific example of the definition of a use case. The values of some parameters are taken from literature as well as from the definition of the ConOps in D3.1 [2]. However, the proposed methodology is fully parametric and can thus be applied to any set of parameters.

3.3.1 Border Control Application

The border control example shown in D4.1 is extended and formally defined according to the syntax described in Section 3.1. A use case with 4 UAS that have to perform some surveillance missions is considered. Therefore, the tuple representing this use case $\mathcal{S} = \langle \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{M}, f, \mathcal{C} \rangle$, is here made up by:

- $\mathcal{A} = \{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4\}$, which is the set of 4 UAS;

The main UAS-related parameters are:

- Max UAS linear velocity: 148.16 km/h = 80 knots;
- Min UASs linear velocity: 9 knots;
- Turn rate : 3 °/s;

- Autonomy: 5 hours;
- $\mathcal{M} = \{M_1, M_2\}$, i.e., the missions to be assigned to each of the 4 UAS. For this particular case, both missions are surveillance missions, but they differ for the trajectory types. Notice also that the number of missions is less than the number of UAS, meaning that there will be different UAS performing the same mission, but obviously overflying different waypoints. Mission parameters are:
 - $M_1 = \langle exploration, params_1 \rangle$, where:
 - $params_{1,1} = \langle take_off, (120, 7) \rangle$;
 - $params_{1,2} = \langle landing, (230, 18) \rangle$;
 - $params_{1,3} = \langle traj_type, random \rangle$;
 - $params_{1,4} = \langle mission_segment_duration, 3h \rangle$;
 - $params_{1,4} = \langle category, NA \rangle$.
 - $M_2 = \langle control, params_2 \rangle$, where:
 - $params_{2,1} = \langle take_off, (1, 2) \rangle$;
 - $params_{2,2} = \langle landing, (120, 10) \rangle$;
 - $params_{2,3} = \langle traj_type, scan \rangle$;
 - $params_{1,4} = \langle mission_segment_duration, 3h \rangle$;
 - $params_{2,4} = \langle category, NA \rangle$.
- task assignment function f is defined to assign one task to each UAS based on some static features (see the Table 1 below);

f mapping	UAS 1	UAS 2	UAS 3	UAS 4
Mission 1	✓	✗	✓	✗
Mission 2	✗	✓	✗	✓

Table 1 Task assignment function

- \mathcal{C} is a set of environment-related parameters, and it is shown in Table 2.
 - volume of operations: 300 Km x 20 Km x 2 Km;
 - semantic map (POI) of the use case: NA;
 - total number of UAS: 4;
 - number of UAS for each type: 1 (fixed wing);

Operations Volume	POI in the use case	# of UAS	# of UAS types
300kmx20kmx2km	✗	4	1

Table 2 Environment definitions

This specification is used to generate the trajectories and to compute the results about separation minima and methods reported in Section 6.

4 Problem Definition

The problems defined in this deliverable are based on the following assumptions that describe the operational setting in which the problems will be addressed.

1. All agent state representations S_i include UAS position in the environment (e.g., GPS location).
2. Special states represent the UAS on the ground, i.e., non in a flight mode.
3. Special action `\emph{wait}` is available when the UAS is on the ground, keeping the agent in such a state and not counting for collision risk analysis.
4. Agents are heterogeneous, i.e., in general, $S_i \neq S_j$ and $A_i \neq A_j$ for different agents (i.e., $i \neq j$).
5. The set of initial states of the agents s_i^0 is consistent with global parameters \mathcal{C} .
6. Tasks are assigned at the beginning of the use case and they do not change during the use case lifetime.
7. The assignment function f assigns a suitable mission to each agent, so that the mission goal can be achieved by the agent.
8. Each mission M_k is independent from all the others, i.e., it can be accomplished independently from any other mission.
9. The same task (mission) can be assigned to multiple agents, but it will be executed by the different agents at different starting times or from different starting positions.
10. Each agent α_i produces exactly one trajectory \mathcal{T}_i .
11. Each trajectory ends in the initial state, i.e. $s_i^{(T)} = s_i^{(0)}$, thus, allowing the agent to repeatedly execute its mission.

With the definition of the use case presented in the previous section and the above-mentioned assumptions, the problems to be solved can be stated as follows.

Problem Definition PD1. Given a use case \mathcal{S} and a set of strategic mitigations, generate a set of trajectories \mathcal{T} that are representative of that use case, respecting such strategic mitigations.

Problem Definition PD2. Given a use case \mathcal{S} , a set of strategic mitigations, and a set of trajectories \mathcal{T} produced in this use case, compute the collision rate of the use case.

Problem Definition PD3. Given a use case \mathcal{S} and a collision-based performance metric (e.g., TLS), compute an optimal set of strategic mitigations (separation minima and methods) for each mission in the use case and with respect to the given performance metrics. In problem PD3, the strategic mitigations (separation minima and methods) can be applied either to the full mission or to each mission segment that is characterized by a different trajectory type. In the latter case, we can refine the problem as follows.

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Problem Definition PD4. Given a use case \mathcal{S} , in which missions are characterized by mission segments associated to different trajectory types, and a collision-based performance metric (e.g., TLS), compute an optimal set of strategic mitigations (separation minima and methods) for each mission segment in the use case and with respect to the given performance metrics.

Problem Definitions **PD3** and **PD4** address the computation of separation minima and methods that is the main objective of this Deliverable and a major overall goal of the BUBBLES project. A methodology to address this problem is presented in the next section. Problem definitions **PD1** and **PD2** can be considered as sub-problems useful to address **PD3** and **PD4**. The solutions of all these problems will also be thus presented in the next section, while Section 5 provides some implementation details and examples of experimental results.

5 Methodology

This section describes the methodology to address the problems defined in the previous section, focusing in particular on **PD3** and using PD1 and PD2 to define appropriate sub-tasks.

5.1 Overview of the approach

The methodology adopted to compute separation minima and methods (PD3) is based on the collision model described in BUBBLES Deliverable D4.1 [1] that uses suitable representative trajectories of a use case (PD1) and a method to estimate the collision risk for such a use case (PD2). Generally speaking, the overall methodology to address PD3 is based on three steps: 1) extracting relevant information from a use case to generate representative trajectories (PD1), 2) estimate the collision risk of such trajectories to create a data set (PD2), 3) train Machine Learning models with created data and use these models to determine separation minima and methods for such a use case.

Figure 5-1 First step

Figure 5-1 shows the first step that consists in the generation of trajectory data relevant to the use case. This task can be performed with different AI tools, such as Reinforcement Learning (RL) and Generative Adversarial Neural Networks (GAN). Other ways of collecting trajectories can also be integrated, like for example the use of simulators or available data that are representative of a given use case.

During the first step, it will be possible to apply strategic mitigations (e.g., based on specific separation minima and methods), so that the generated trajectories will be consistent with such specifications.

Figure 5-2 Second step

From the data generated in the first step, the BUBBLES collision model can be applied to estimate the collision rate (see also Figure 5-2), by using the formula:

$$F_{collision} = F_{conflict} P(collision | conflict)(1)$$

As described in D4.1 [1], only the term $F_{conflict}$ depends on the specific use case and thus on the generated trajectories. Consequently, the estimation of $F_{conflict}$ given the input trajectories can be separated from the estimation of $P(collision | conflict)$ that does not depend on the trajectories. By simulating several situations (including strategic mitigations) occurring in the considered use case, a dataset of information relating the parameters of the use case and the strategic mitigations with the conflict rate can be collected. In other words, steps 1 and 2 (i.e., trajectory generation and collision rate estimation) can be repeated multiple times under different conditions (including different parameters of the strategic mitigations) to collect a suitable data set for the considered use case.

Figure 5-3 Third step – training

Figure 5-4 Third step - prediction

Finally, in the third step, the dataset generated in the previous steps are first used to train machine learning models (Figure 5-3) and then use the trained models to compute separation minima and methods for a given TLS (Figure 5-4).

More specifically, a target function suitable to return separation minima and methods from the other parameters collected in the data set is defined and collected data are used for training one or more machine learning models to approximate such a function. Then, the predictions of the trained model are used to compute separation minima and methods for the given use case and a pre-defined TLS.

The overall approach is summarized in the following steps:

Input: Use case specification, TLS

Output: separation minima and methods for each mission segment of each UAS

Algorithmic steps:

1. Initialize a database containing all the results of the experiments.
2. Repeat until sufficient data are obtained.
 - a. Choose appropriate separation minima and methods.
 - b. Generate trajectories (taking into account the chosen separation methods).
 - c. Compute the Frequency of Conflict from sampled trajectories.
 - d. Compute the Frequency of Collisions.
 - e. Store results of the experiments in the database.
3. Train Machine Learning (ML) models with above generated data able to determine separation methods and minima.
4. Use predictions of the trained ML models to return separation methods and minima for the mission segments that guarantee the desired TLS.

The following sections describe in more detail each of the above-mentioned steps.

5.2 Trajectory generation

Trajectories are generated by taking into account the use case specifications and considering specific strategic mitigations given in terms of separation methods and minima. In particular, the separation methods described in Section 2 will be properly encoded in the algorithms used to generate the trajectories, in order to guarantee compliance to them.

Different algorithms for trajectory generation will be implemented and all of them can contribute to the generation of representative trajectories for a given use case. The overall trajectory of a mission is in general formed by concatenating different pieces of trajectories coming from different behaviors operated during the development of the mission. For example, a mission can require the UAS to fly to a target in a linear direction, then to hover for some time over such a target, then to execute a specific flight pattern, and finally to come back to the home position with a linear flight mode. This overall trajectory can be composed by four sub-trajectories possibly generated with different approaches.

This section, briefly summarizes the main approaches that will be used to generate such trajectories, or more specifically, pieces of trajectories that can be combined to generate overall mission trajectories.

Control based approaches. These approaches are based on the definition of a control law that the agents will follow and that will drive the generation of the corresponding trajectory. A linear control law, for example, can control the movement of a UAS in a linear direction until a specific target is reached. Controllers can be augmented with artificial noise in order to take into account typical position and manoeuvring uncertainties arising in real systems.

Reinforcement Learning (RL) based approaches. These approaches are based on modelling the mission as a RL problem and use RL algorithms to determine optimal behavior with respect to a reward function defining the mission goals [10]. In contrast with Control-based approaches, in RL-based approaches it is not necessary to specify the transition function and the reward function that characterize the environment, but it is sufficient to provide a simulator implementing such functions. RL approaches on the other hand require computational resources to train the optimal policies and suitable methods that guarantee high scalability with respect to the size of the environment, to the number of UAS, and to the complexity of the use case. RL approaches can also be integrated with knowledge representation and reasoning techniques in order to exploit logical formalisms to define agents' behavior (such as in [11]).

Generative Adversarial Networks (GAN) based approaches. These approaches are based on using GAN to learn a model of trajectories and generate new trajectories that are similar to the ones used in the training phase. GAN are very useful to increase the scalability of the method, since they can learn how to generate new synthetic trajectories that will not be distinguishable from the ones provided in the training phase [12]. In other words, after a set of trajectories are generated and used for training a GAN model, such a model can generate similar trajectories with a much less computational effort.

The set of all the trajectories for all the agents is denoted with $\mathcal{T} = \{\tau_1, \dots, \tau_n\}$, with $|\mathcal{T}| = n$, i.e., as many as the UASs in the environment.

For what concerns the data flights, they are stored based on the available Eurocontrol dataset. The most important data related to a single flight (identified by a unique ID) are:

- ID (the unique number identifying a UAS flight);
- Time (the elapsed time for the current flight);
- X ('x' coordinate);
- Y ('y' coordinate);
- Z ('z' coordinate);

Obviously, other data can be stored and considered, such as orientation, linear and angular velocity of the UAS.

5.3 Derivation of the Frequency of Conflict

For each experimental configuration, after a set of trajectories have been generated as illustrated in the previous section, the frequency of conflict is estimated by applying the BUBBLES collision risk model that has been fully described in Deliverable D4.1 [1].

More specifically, a Monte Carlo approach is used to sample the set of trajectories and to estimate the probability of a conflict and the conflict frequency. The process can be repeated until a predefined standard deviation is achieved to guarantee the significance of the result.

5.4 Derivation of the Frequency of Collisions

While the Frequency of Conflict depends on the generated trajectories, the probability of collisions can be estimated by just taking into account pairwise characteristics of the aircrafts involved in a conflict. This step has also been extensively described in Deliverable D4.1 [1].

The collision rate (i.e., frequency of collision) can thus be calculated with Equation (1) from the frequency of conflict determined with the Monte Carlo approach described above and from the probability of collisions determined through a pair-wise analysis of the involved UAS, as explained in D4.1 [1].

5.5 Store results of the experiments in the database

All the experiments including the steps of defining separation minima and methods, generating the trajectories, and computing frequency of conflict and frequency of collision are stored in a database that collects all these results and will be used for training Machine Learning models.

A proper structure of the database has been defined to include the following kinds of information:

- use case related parameters
- separation minima and methods
- results from the collision risk model (frequency of conflict, probability of a collision given a conflict, and frequency of collision)

5.6 Train a Machine Learning model

After the generation of a suitable database containing the results of some experiments in the chosen use case, this database can be used to train one or more Machine Learning (ML) models to determine separation minima and methods.

Several ML models can be defined and different ML approaches will be implemented and compared, including the ones described below.

Support Vector Machines (SVM) models. SVM are suitable methods for classification and regressions that can be effectively applied with relatively small data sets and when the target function can be effectively modelled with a kernel.

Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) models. ANN can be effectively used when the target function cannot be easily characterized by a kernel model. In other words, with ANN the requirement of guessing a specific kernel function (needed for example, in SVM models) can be skipped, but several other hyper-parameters related to the definition of the layout of the network have to be set.

Deep Neural Networks (DNN) models. DNN are extensions of ANN exploiting the ability of deep networks to better model a target function [13][13]. With DNN, also the number of model parameters can be significantly higher with respect to a shallow ANN, thus requiring much more training data to obtain reasonable performance.

Ensemble models. Different ML models can be integrated with ensemble techniques (e.g., voting, bagging, boosting) [14] to achieve better estimation from multiple predictions. Ensemble models are useful to merge different features and capabilities of different ML models, usually providing better performance than each single model.

5.7 Compute separation methods and minima

The final step of the procedure is the computation of separation minima and methods for the considered use case and given a TLS. More precisely, the method will return specific values of separation for each mission segment of each UAS.

This computation is performed by using the prediction capabilities of the ML models trained with data from the experiments. More specifically, the ML models will receive in input the TLS and will return in output the separation minima and methods for each mission segment that, according to the provided experimental data, will guarantee the desired TLS in an optimal way.

This procedure can be implemented in different ways, depending on the features of the trained ML models. For example, if different models are trained for different separation methods, each trained model will predict a value of separation minima for the given TLS and a complete table reporting the separation minima for each separation method will be produced.

More in general, if multiple strategic mitigation measures are applied during the training phase, the computation of separation minima will be reported for each strategic mitigation measure considered.

6 Implementation and example results

This section describes some implementation details of the methodology described in the previous section as well as some examples of experimental results in a specific use case, extending the one provided in Deliverable D4.1 [1].

The software tools developed to implement the above methodology are listed below:

- **use case management tools:** software tools to write and manage use case definitions and data structures used in other software packages.
- **UAS trajectory generation:** software package to generate sets of trajectories for a specific use case.
- **Multi-UAS OpenAI Gym environment:** software package to define Multi-UAS environments using the OpenAI Gym framework and suitable for the application of Reinforcement Learning algorithms to determine mission control strategies.
- **BUBBLES risk model:** software package to estimate trajectory-based conflict frequency and collision rate.
- **BUBBLES risk learning:** machine learning components to train risk analysis models from and to predict separation minima and methods.

All the software developed will be released in an open-source format, under the licensing conditions specified in the project Data Management Plan (Deliverable D8.1 [15]).

6.1 Results in the Border Control Application

Referring to the example described in Section §3.3.1, some experimental results obtained with the software implementation of the proposed methodology are illustrated and commented here.

In the use cases reported here, the UAS are assumed to fly at the same altitude (for example, considering a situation in which vertical separation has been already carried out) and take off at random times that are independent of each other. Under this assumption, 2D trajectories can be considered and the sampling approach for computing the frequency of conflict described in Deliverable D4.1 [1] can be used.

Four different use cases in this application have been analyzed to show different results obtained in different conditions. Results are compared in order to show how different choices of missions and of separation minima and methods affect the result in computing the frequency of conflicts.

Use case 1

This first use case (an example of trajectories is shown in Figure 6-1) is the same as the one in D4.1 [1] (Section §3.4.3), in which the UAS are operating in the environment without following any mission and not being restricted by any separation method.

Figure 6-1 First use case with free flights.

Use case 2

In the second use case (with an example of trajectories depicted in Figure 6-2), the UAS follow the missions described in Section §3.3.1 without any separation method. The missions are composed of two types of trajectories: linear and scan. In the figures, crosses and circles represent respectively the take-off and landing points: blue points indicate the ‘scan’ trajectory type, while the violet ones are related to the ‘random’ trajectory type.

Figure 6-2 Second use case (no separation method applied).

Use case 3

The third use case shows the UAS following the missions as in the previous case, but applying also a separation method based on delimiting the scanning area. The design of the separation method and the separation minima are reported in Figure 6-3, with envelopes of the scanning phase of the two missions colored with 4 colors (each one associated with a UAS) and pairwise separation minima indicated as dashed lines. Notice that, in this example, the linear trajectories (first phase of the missions) are not subject to any separation (so they can possibly conflict with the scanning trajectories). More specifically, four envelopes constraining the trajectories based on their mission

type have been defined. For green and red 'random' trajectories boxes are respectively given by $([0,125],[10,12])$ and $([180,300],[10,12])$, while the blue and red 'scan' trajectories are delimited respectively by $([0,300],[15,18])$ and $([0,300],[2,5.5])$. Each tuple is made up by two intervals, the first one is related to the minimum and maximum values which could occur along the X axis, while the second one refers to the minimum and maximum values which could occur along the Y axis.

The pairwise separation minima are thus (5, 55, 3): 5 Km from blue 'scan' to green and red 'random', 55 Km from green 'rand' to red 'rand' and 3 Km from orange 'scan' and green and red 'random'.

Figure 6-3 Separation method for use cases 3 and 4.

An example of generated trajectories is shown in Figure 6-4 with colors corresponding to the separation areas in Figure 6-3. A noisy execution of the missions has been simulated, so the trajectories may slightly get outside the envelopes due for example to position and navigation noise and errors. Moreover, as for the other use cases, we assume the starting times of the missions for each UAS to be random and independent of each other.

Figure 6-4 Third use case (with separation method).

Use case 4

The fourth use case differs from use case 3 only in the values of separation minima, following the same separation method shown above. The corresponding trajectories are shown in Figure 6-5. The envelopes delimiting respectively ‘random’ trajectories are the same used in the previous case. Also, the envelope used for orange ‘scan’ trajectory is the same as in the use case 3; therefore, the only difference here is given by the envelope which delimits the blue ‘scan’ trajectory that is $([0,300],[16,18])$. Thus, the separation minima are increased to (5, 55, 4), with the same meaning of the values explained for use case 3.

Figure 6-5 Fourth use case (with separation method).

For each of these use cases we applied the collision risk model described in Deliverable D4.1 [1] and in particular the procedure to estimate the frequency of collisions that is the term that depends on the trajectories (and thus on the mission and on the separation measures). While, as already discussed in D4.1 [1], the probability of collision given a conflict does not depend on the trajectories.

Therefore, in the following we focus only on the different values of the conflict rate, that can be transformed in the collision rate by multiplying it by a constant factor with respect to the trajectories.

	Conflict threshold 1 Km avg (stdev)	Conflict threshold 2 Km avg (stdev)
Use case 1	7.24E-04 (1.35E-04)	2.32E-03 (3.88E-04)
Use case 2	5.55E-04 (1.26E-04)	2.20E-03 (5.06E-04)
Use case 3 (5, 55, 3)	1.30E-04 (2.17E-05)	5.39E-04 (7.41E-05)
Use case 4 (5, 55, 4)	8.69E-05 (1.09E-05)	5.05E-04 (9.57E-05)

Table 3 Conflict frequency in the four use cases.

Table 3 shows the results of the computation of conflict frequency in the four use cases for two different values of the conflict threshold (1 Km and 2 Km). As expected, the values differ in each use case as a result of applying different constraints on the generation of the trajectories. It is also evident that conflict frequency decreases when specific missions are considered and increasing separation measures are adopted.

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These experiments show that the proposed methodology can suitably estimate the conflict frequency (and consequently the collision rate) from a set of generated trajectories that are representative of the considered use case (considering in particular different missions and trajectory types) and depend on the chosen separation minima and methods.

As explained in the previous section, by running several simulations of this kind with different separation minima and methods, it is possible to collect data and train a machine learning model to predict values in new cases. In this way, it is also possible to revert the problem and establish separation minima and methods to achieve a given TLS.

For example, referring to the separation method and the numerical examples shown above and to a TLS corresponding to a conflict frequency of $1E-4$ for a conflict threshold of 1 Km (which is an intermediate value between use cases 3 and 4), suitable values for separation minima between orange 'scan' and green and red 'random' can be computed as interpolation of the conflict frequencies $8.69E-5$ and $1.30E-4$, thus 3.3 Km. So, in this simple case, separation minima (5, 55, 3.3) will correspond to the desired conflict frequency $1E-4$.

In a more general case, both separation methods and several values for separation minima must be computed and it may be impractical or impossible to use interpolation. The ML model prediction can be considered as an extension of the previous simple example, in which the trained model will be able to provide predictions for separation minima and methods that guarantee a given TLS.

6.2 Discussion

The results presented in this section show just an example of the applicability of the proposed methodology. The system implementation is fully parametric and allows for configuring several different use cases with little effort. In this way, it is possible to generate representative data in different conditions, as well as analyse specific situations.

Although generated in an abstract way, the trajectories are useful to provide a good estimate of the conflict frequency. On the other hand, this abstraction layer allows for a fast and scalable method that can simulate hundreds or thousands of situations in a few seconds.

Additional work is required to map the requirements of a complex use case, including several missions, different types of UAS, different separation measures, etc. to the software proposed in this deliverable and more advanced AI based trajectory generation methods can be evaluated.

Indeed, a major goal of BUBBLES project, in particular within the tasks of WP5, will be to validate the proposed methodology in realistic scenarios and to provide additional guidelines, specifications, and requirements for its integration in a U-space separation management service.

7 References

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